

A VISION TRANSFORMER AND RESNET ENSEMBLE METHOD BASED ON THE UNIMATCH SEMI-SUPERVISED SEGMENTATION FRAMEWORK FOR THE FETAL ULTRASOUND GRAND CHALLENGE

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ABSTRACT

Accurate segmentation of cervical muscle ultrasound images is crucial for analyzing deep structures, functional assessment, and personalized treatment monitoring. However, manual annotation of transvaginal ultrasound images of cervical structures is labor-intensive and time-consuming, limiting the acquisition of large-scale labeled datasets. To address this challenge, semi-supervised learning approaches have shown potential by leveraging both labeled and unlabeled data, enabling the extraction of useful information from unannotated cases. In this paper, we focus on the semi-supervised ultrasound cervical image segmentation problem for the 2025 International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging (ISBI) Fetal Ultrasound Grand Challenge. We aim to design high-quality segmentation models using a small number of labeled images and a large number of unlabeled images. We train two U-Net variant models using the UniMatch semi-supervised segmentation framework and utilize an ensemble model to generate pseudo labels for augmenting training data. Experiments on the validation set show that this approach outperforms using only the UniMatch semi-supervised segmentation method. The code is available at https://github.com/Ailerx/ISBI_2025_IUGC.

Index Terms— Semi-Supervised Segmentation, UniMatch, ultrasound image, PVT_v2_b1, ResNet34d

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of medical image analysis, cervical image segmentation is a task of great significance, especially in ultrasound imaging [1]. Ultrasound imaging, as a non-invasive, convenient, and cost-effective medical imaging modality, is widely used in obstetrics and gynecology, reproductive medicine, as well as in the screening and diagnosis of cervical diseases [2]. The cervix is an important component of the female reproductive system, and its structural and functional abnormalities are closely related to a variety of diseases, such as cervical cancer and cervical incompetence. Accurate segmentation of cervical images can provide clinicians with key anatomical information to assist in diagnosis, treatment planning, and surgical

navigation, thereby improving the quality and efficiency of medical services[3].

However, cervical ultrasound image segmentation faces numerous challenges. First, the physical properties of ultrasound imaging lead to issues such as noise, artifacts, and low contrast in the images, making the boundaries of the cervix difficult to distinguish clearly. Second, the shape and position of the cervix vary significantly among different individuals and under different physiological conditions, adding to the complexity of segmentation. Moreover, the acquisition conditions of ultrasound images (such as probe angle and pressure) can also have a significant impact on image quality, further increasing the difficulty of the segmentation task [4].

In recent years, with the rapid development of deep learning [5] technology, especially Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), significant achievements have been made in medical image segmentation tasks. Deep learning-based segmentation methods can automatically learn features from images, thereby achieving precise segmentation of target areas. However, these methods typically require a large amount of annotated data for model training, and in the field of ultrasound cervical images, high-quality annotated data is often scarce and costly to obtain. Moreover, the generalization ability of deep learning models still needs to be further improved when facing different devices, different patient populations, and different imaging conditions.

2. METHODS

2.1. UniMatch: End-to-End Semi-Supervised Segmentation Method

UniMatch [6] is an innovative method proposed in the field of semi-supervised semantic segmentation. Its core idea is to re-examine the weak-to-strong consistency principle in semi-supervised semantic segmentation. UniMatch significantly enhances model performance by introducing feature-level augmentation and dual-stream enhancement strategies. This method not only simplifies model design but also promotes knowledge sharing across different tasks. Furthermore, UniMatch employs a parameter-free matching layer, which not only improves model efficiency but also enhances its gener-

Fig. 1: Overall Process Flow of Our Method

alization capability. By incorporating self-attention layers, UniMatch can effectively propagate high-quality prediction results to hard-to-match areas, thereby improving overall segmentation accuracy.

2.2. Workflow Introduction

We utilize PVT_v2_b1 [7] and ResNet34d [8], both pre-trained on ImageNet1K [9], as the backbones for our UNet [10] models. Our final approach is based on an ensemble of these two models, which we refer to as PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet, respectively. Given that our training dataset consists of only 50 labeled images and 450 unlabeled images, the number of directly usable images is quite limited. To address this, we have adopted the highly effective semi-supervised segmentation method, UniMatch, which is particularly renowned in the field of image segmentation. This end-to-end segmentation approach has saved us considerable time that would otherwise be spent on building a semi-supervised segmentation framework.

Specifically, we initially trained the PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet models using the UniMatch segmentation method. This approach allowed the models to effectively learn from unlabeled image data. We tested the performance of ResNet34d_UNet trained under the UniMatch semi-supervised method and found it to be inferior to ResNet34d. Interestingly, when subsequently training with pseudo labels in a fully supervised manner, the performance of ResNet34d_UNet was not as good as that of ResNet34d. We also briefly experimented with training solely on the 50 labeled images using a fully supervised approach, which resulted in a Dice score approximately 5% lower compared to using the semi-supervised training method.

After completing the semi-supervised training, we inte-

grated the best-performing models, PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet, to infer on the 450 unlabeled images for generating pseudo labels. Subsequently, we manually selected high-quality pseudo-labeled images to augment our labeled training data. This process of filtering pseudo labels was repeated twice. Following the first round of augmenting pseudo-labeled data, we obtained a total of 200 labeled images (50 with real labels and 150 with high-quality pseudo labels). Recognizing that fully supervised methods allow models to learn more from the data, we trained the models on these 200 labeled images using a fully supervised approach. We then integrated the trained PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet models once again to infer on the 450 unlabeled images for generating new pseudo labels. This second round of inference yielded 400 additional high-quality pseudo labels.

Finally, we conducted another round of fully supervised training on the PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet models using the expanded dataset of 450 labeled images (including 50 images with real labels). The integrated model resulting from this training served as our final model for the ultimate evaluation.

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Challenge Dataset

The training dataset consists of 500 cervical ultrasound images (including the anterior and posterior lips of the cervix), out of which 50 images are labeled, and 450 images are unlabeled. The validation set includes 90 labeled images, while the test set comprises 300 labeled images.

3.2. Data Augmentation

For the labeled images, we applied data augmentation techniques such as RandomFlip, RandomRotation, and ColorJitter. For the unlabeled images, in addition to RandomFlip, RandomRotation, and ColorJitter, we also used CutMix. Given that the image size is 336×544 pixels, we refrained from performing Crop and Resize operations on the images.

3.3. Training Details

We used an input size of 336×544 pixels and reserved 10% of the training samples for validation. For labeled images, we employed a weighted loss function combining cross-entropy and Dice loss. For unlabeled images, we used only the Dice loss. The learning rate was set to 0.01, with a cosine annealing scheduler. We utilized the AdamW [11] optimizer and set the batch size to 4. All models were trained for 150 epochs on a single NVIDIA 4090 GPU.

3.4. Model Performance Comparison

We tested a variety of models including the pure UNet, EfficientNetB3_UNet, and mxvitb1 and mxvitb2 models from the segmentation-models-pytorch semantic segmentation library. Below are the performance metrics of the models on the validation leaderboard:

Model_name	Dice	Hd95	time
UNet	0.88719	44.572	20.4830
EfficientNetb3_UNet	0.77934	68.978	43.5421
PVT_v2_b1_UNet	0.9297	21.977	48.3728
ResNet34d_UNet	0.9252	21.9037	60.0524
smp_mxvitb1	0.9272	34.706	67.261
smp_mxvitb2	0.9307	19.9684	122.599

Table 1: Performance comparison of different models on the validation set.

All the aforementioned models were trained under identical training configurations and on the same training dataset. Although the mxvitb2 model demonstrated the best performance on the validation set, its integration with either PVT_v2_b1_UNet or ResNet34d_UNet led to a decrease in validation scores. Additionally, mxvitb2 performed worse on the test leaderboard compared to the ensemble method of PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet. We hypothesize that the large number of parameters in the mxvitb2 model caused it to overfit the training data. Consequently, we chose the ensemble model of PVT_v2_b1_UNet and ResNet34d_UNet as our final test model.

Fig. 2: Model’s Average Dice Score Curve

Fig. 3: Model’s Validation Loss Curve

Fig. 4: Model’s Training Loss Curve

We further conducted a performance visualization analysis of several fully supervised models based on pseudo-labels, including smp_mxvitb2, PVT_v2_b1_UNet, ResNet34d_UNet,

ResNet34_UNet, and ResNet50_UNet. However, due to the storage policy of the competition platform, the validation scores of ResNet50_UNet and ResNet34_UNet were deleted, and their corresponding test scores were not recorded in time. Therefore, the test results of these two models are not presented in Table 1.

4. CONCLUSION

The proposed ensemble semi-supervised framework effectively addresses the scarcity of annotated cervical ultrasound data. By integrating UniMatch with iterative pseudo-label refinement, it significantly improves segmentation performance. The complementary feature representation of Vision Transformer and ResNet enhances model robustness. This method provides an extensible solution for medical image segmentation. Future work may explore advanced pseudo-label filtering mechanisms and cross-modal fusion strategies.

5. REFERENCES

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